

1 **TITLE:**
2 Evaluation of Commercial-Off-The-Shelf Wrist Wearables to Estimate Stress on Students
3

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20
21 **KEYWORDS:**
22 wrist-wearables, quantification, multimodal analytics, stress detection, machine learning, e-
23 learning.

24
25 **SHORT ABSTRACT:**
26 A protocol to evaluate solutions based on commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) wrist wearables to
27 estimate stress in students is proposed. The protocol is carried out in two phases, an initial
28 laboratory-based stress induction test, and a monitoring stage taking place in the classroom
29 while the student is performing academic activities.

30
31 **LONG ABSTRACT:**
32 Wearable commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) devices have become popular during the last years
33 to monitor sports activities, primarily among young people. These devices include sensors to
34 gather data on physiological signals such as heart rate, skin temperature or galvanic skin
35 response. By applying data analytics techniques to these kinds of signals, it is possible to obtain
36 estimations of higher-level aspects of human behavior. In the literature, there are several works
37 describing the use of physiological data collected using clinical devices to obtain information on
38 sleep patterns or stress. However, it is still an open question whether data captured using COTS
39 wrist wearables is sufficient to characterize the learners' psychological state in educational
40 settings. This paper discusses a protocol to evaluate stress estimation from data obtained using
41 COTS wrist wearables. The protocol is carried out in two phases. The first stage consists of a
42 controlled laboratory experiment, where a mobile app is used to induce different stress levels
43 in a student by means of a relaxing video, a Stroop Color and Word test, a Paced Auditory Serial
44 Addition test, and a hyperventilation test. The second phase is carried out in the classroom,

45 where stress is analyzed while performing several academic activities, namely attending to
46 theoretical lectures, doing exercises and other individual activities, and taking short tests and
47 exams. In both cases, both quantitative data obtained from COTS wrist wearables and
48 qualitative data gathered by means of questionnaires are considered. This protocol involves a
49 simple and consistent method with a stress induction app and questionnaires, requiring a
50 limited participation of support staff.

51

52 **INTRODUCTION:**

53 State-of-the-art wearable technologies are widely available, and their application environments
54 are continuously expanding. We can find in the market many different devices, among which
55 COTS wrist wearables¹, such as smart watches and smart bands, are popular among athletes as
56 a personal physical fitness monitoring tool². By applying data analytic techniques, the data
57 obtained using these devices can be processed to provide indicators such as general physical
58 state, sleep quality or recovery factor. The demonstrated applicability in this area raised
59 interest in the academic community about their possible application to other fields, especially
60 in the health domain^{3,4}, although the strict requirements of clinical trials limit their
61 introduction. However, in a less demanding context such as education, we can find in the
62 literature recent investigations involving the use of different types of wearable devices, both
63 related to teaching activities^{5,6} and to the estimation of certain characteristics of the student
64 such as sleep patterns⁷, or the analysis of students' engagement in different educational
65 activities⁸.

66

67 In our case, we focus on analyzing COTS wrist wearable devices as means to collect
68 physiological signals that would eventually facilitate stress estimation, which in turn is a key
69 aspect in educational contexts. Stress has a relevant influence in the development of academic
70 activities and overall students' performance. For example, stress levels are directly related to
71 the onset of the burnout syndrome in students⁹⁻¹¹, and high stress levels are especially relevant
72 during the freshman year, where drop-out rates between 20% and 30%^{12,13} are common.
73 Detecting and controlling stress indicators could dramatically improve academic performance.

74

75 The use of COTS wrist wearable devices is justified because they have sensors that provide
76 information on physiological signals that have been widely used by the scientific community in
77 stress assessment and detection. Some of the signals referred to in the literature used for this
78 purpose include heart rate (HR)¹⁴, heart rate variability¹⁵, skin temperature (ST)¹⁶, respiration¹⁴,
79 and galvanic skin response (GSR)¹⁷. These signals can be collected by COTS wrist wearables.
80 However, they do not offer the same performance as clinical devices. There are differences
81 related to the accuracy of sensors among devices¹⁸⁻²¹. Nevertheless, previous works¹⁸⁻²¹ have
82 shown that, in a slow movement scenario, COTS wrist wearable sensors have error patterns
83 similar to specialized devices.

84

85 The aim of this paper is to introduce a protocol to evaluate different solutions for stress
86 estimation in students using COTS wrist wearables. There are many arrangements that can be
87 proposed to estimate stress levels, involving the use of different wrist wearable devices and
88 data analytics techniques, and more specifically machine learning algorithms. COTS wrist

89 wearables are characterized by their high fragmentation, heterogeneity and interoperability
90 problems²². Three companies have an aggregated market share of almost 50%²³, but many
91 other companies account for much smaller individual market shares, with an aggregated share
92 above 50%. On the other hand, in terms of heterogeneity, not all wearables have the same
93 number and type of sensors, with accelerometers and h sensors being the most common, and
94 ST's and GSR's being only present in 5% of the devices studied. As for interoperability, there are
95 different operating systems and data collection approaches that are not compatible with each
96 other. As for the machine learning techniques that can be applied to estimate stress from the
97 data collected by means of a wrist device, there are many options available²⁴, including decision
98 trees, neural networks, nearest neighbor approaches, Naïve Bayes classifiers, *etc.* To sum up,
99 there is a great variety of solutions that may be developed for stress estimation, so it is
100 instrumental to design an evaluation protocol to facilitate the comparison among different
101 tentative options to eventually select the most suitable in a given context.

102
103 For the implementation of the protocol, several tools are needed (**Figure 1**). First, a COTS wrist
104 wearable device is needed to fetch physiological data. This wearable device should have at least
105 HR monitoring capabilities, but additional sensors are desirable (*e.g.*, accelerometer, ST, GSR
106 sensors). Second, a smartphone running the PhysiologicalSignal app is required to collect the
107 data captured by the wearable device. Third, a tablet running the StressTest app is needed to
108 run stress induction exercises (the smartphone could be used instead the tablet for this
109 purpose). Fourth, some questionnaires to collect qualitative data on students' perception on
110 stress. Fifth, a server with a Web service²⁵ to perform data collection and pre-processing, and a
111 Web dashboard to show the evolution of the signals. And finally, a data analytics package²⁶ to
112 process the data collected about students using machine learning techniques.

113
114 The evaluation protocol is organized into two phases. The first one, the laboratory phase, is
115 carried out in a comfortable room, where different stress levels (*i.e.*, "relax", "concentrated
116 stress" and "stress") are induced to a target subject (a student) through several common stress-
117 inducing tasks. The second part takes place in the classroom, and it involves monitoring the
118 student during the accomplishment of several academic activities: theoretical explanations,
119 individual activities, short tests, exams, *etc.* During the implementation of this protocol, the
120 subject's physiological signals are captured by means of a wrist device. Finally, these signals are
121 processed by machine learning algorithms to provide estimations on the level of stress.

122
123 During the laboratory phase, the StressTest app is used to induce different stress levels. This
124 app guides the subject to the completion of four different tasks. The first task is to create a
125 baseline for stress analysis. In this task, the student visualizes a 4-minute relaxing video in
126 which different shots of a sunset on a bridge are shown. The second task is an adaptation of the
127 Stroop Color and Word Test²⁷ (SCWT). Every two seconds, the subject must choose the color in
128 which the name of a color is painted (red, green, orange, blue and purple). Several buttons
129 located at the bottom of the screen containing the initial letter of each color are available for
130 the subject to choose the painted color at each time. For example, the button that refers to
131 blue depicts the letter B. In our case, this test is divided into three different levels of difficulty.
132 For the first level (SCWT1), the colored "words of colors" will appear in the same order as the

133 buttons, so color and name match directly. This level is taken as baseline, as it does not involve
134 any difficulty and the subject should only press the buttons properly, always in the same order.
135 For the second level (SCWT2), the colored “words of colors” appear randomly, but the
136 correspondence between name and color is maintained. Every time the subject fails a beep is
137 emitted, and if two errors are made, the correct color score will be reset. For the last, most
138 difficult level (SCWT3), name and color do not match. In this way this level is intended to be
139 more complex and stressful for the subject. The third task consists on the Paced Auditory Serial
140 Addition test (PASAT)²⁸, which measures how the student experiences a concentration test.
141 During this task, a sequence of consecutive numbers is played aloud, and the student must add
142 the last two numbers and write the result in the provided on-screen box before listening to the
143 next number. In this task, if the subject makes a mistake, a disturbing event occurs to generate
144 stress (two numbers sound at the same time or a long period of silence in maintained). In this
145 case, if three errors are committed, the sum account will be reset. The fourth task consists on a
146 hyperventilation activity to induce the same variation in the physiological signals that would
147 provoke a stressful situation¹⁷. At the end of each task and level, the subject has to indicate the
148 level of perceived stress, using the application itself, according to a 5-value Likert scale.

149
150 During the classroom phase, students carry out their ordinary academic activities together with
151 the rest of their classmates. The protocol focuses on the stress levels that occur during
152 classroom-specific activities. At the end of the lecture, a brief questionnaire (Annex 1) is
153 completed by the student to indicate the perceived level of stress in the several activities
154 according to a 5-value scale.

155 156 **PROTOCOL:**

157
158 All methods described below have been approved by the regional government of Galicia’s
159 committee for research ethics of Pontevedra-Vigo-Ourense (reg. code 2017/336). The protocol
160 was implemented for first year students at the School of Telecommunication Engineering -
161 University of Vigo, both in a comfortable laboratory room and in several lectures and practice
162 sessions of a bachelor’s degree course on Computer Architectures.

163 164 **1. Prepare the Devices**

- 165
- 166 1.1. Connect the smartphone and tablet device to a stable internet connection.
- 167
- 168 1.2. Turn on Bluetooth communications in the smartphone.
- 169
- 170 1.3. In the smartphone, search in the corresponding official app store the wrist wearable
171 application. Download and install it.
- 172
- 173 1.4. In the smartphone, search for the PhysiologicalSignals app to capture physiological
174 signals. Download and install it.

175
176 Note: Currently, the app is a beta version and access can be provided by request.

177
178 1.5. In the tablet, search for the StressTest app to be used in the research laboratory
179 experiments. Download and install it.

180
181 Note: Currently, the app is a beta version and access can be provided by request.

182
183 1.6. Turn on the COTS wrist wearable device and place the wearable.

184
185 1.7. In the smartphone, open the official COTS wrist wearable application.

186
187 Note: The app will proceed to synchronize the wearable device with the smartphone. In some
188 devices, an e-mail address is required.

189
190 1.8. In the smartphone, open the PhysiologicalSignals app.

191
192 1.8.1. In case of being notified of a sensor access request, accept it.

193
194 1.8.2. Check the device. Wait for the PhysiologicalSignals app to display the word **Weared** in
195 green.

196
197 Note: This indicate that the wearable device has been detected and therefore the transmission
198 of information from the sensors to the smartphone is enabled. If this message does not appear
199 repeat from step 1.6.

200 201 **2. The Laboratory Phase**

202
203 2.1. Prepare the laboratory setting. Choose a comfortable and non-disturbing room without
204 distracting noise and with a comfortable temperature (between 22 °C and 26 °C).

205
206 2.2. Turn on the wrist wearable device, place it around the subject's non-dominant wrist and
207 place the headphones on the head of the student. Fit the wearable tightly but comfortably
208 around the wrist.

209
210 2.3. Connect the smartphone and tablet to a stable internet connection and verify that the
211 Bluetooth connection is active.

212
213 2.4. In the smartphone, launch the PhysiologicalSignals app.

214
215 2.4.1. Wait for the app to display the word **Weared** in green.

216
217 2.4.2. Select the **Change User** option in the left configuration menu and provide the ID of the
218 subject who will complete the tests and click **Save**.

219
220 2.5. In a laptop, access the dashboard and enter the test administrator's ID and password.

221
222 Note: Currently, for private and security concerns, access to the dashboard is only available
223 under request.
224
225 2.5.1. Select the subject ID and the subject's stress tab.
226
227 2.5.2. Check the physiological signals evolution and wait for the wearable device to reach
228 thermal stability before starting the experiment.
229
230 Note: The thermal stability is identified as a plateau in the graph.
231
232 2.6. In the tablet, launch the StressTest application.
233
234 2.6.1. Explain to the subject the four laboratory tasks. Show some of the screens and actions
235 to perform during each one of the tasks.
236
237 Note: This is very important, because the subject should feel stressed or relaxed in accordance
238 to the performed activities, and not fear or concern about what is going to happen.
239
240 2.6.2. Tell the student not to rest their arms on the table and to use the hand where the
241 wearable device is placed to perform the activities.
242
243 2.6.3. Enter the same user ID as in step 2.4.2 and click the arrow.
244
245 2.7. Launch the video task and give full control to the student.
246
247 2.7.1. Observe that the task is carried out without incident.
248
249 2.7.2. When the task is finished, check that the subject provides the perceived stress.
250
251 2.8. Launch the Stroop Color task (SCWT) consecutively for levels 1, 2 and 3.
252
253 2.8.1. For each level, observe that the subtask is carried out without incident.
254
255 2.8.2. When each subtask is finished, check that the subject provides the perceived stress.
256
257 2.8.3. Only for level 3 and only in case the subject does not solve it after 4 minutes, terminate
258 the task by pressing the arrow located at the top of the screen.
259
260 2.9. Launch the Paced Auditory Serial Addition test (PASAT).
261
262 2.9.1. Observe that the task is carried out without incident.
263

264 2.9.2. In case the subject does not solve the PASAT test after 4 minutes, terminate the task by
265 pressing the arrow located at the top of the screen.

266
267 2.9.3. When the task is finished, check that the subject provides the perceived stress.
268

269 2.10. Launch the Hyperventilation test.
270

271 2.10.1. Observe the evolution of HR using the dashboard. If physiological signals do not change
272 significantly, ask the subject to increase inspiration and expiration rates gradually.
273

274 2.10.2. In case the subject feels dizziness or uncomfortable halt this task. In any case, complete
275 the task after four minutes.
276

277 2.10.3. When the task is finished, check that the subject provides the perceived stress.
278

279 **3. The Classroom Phase**

280
281 3.1. Turn on the wrist wearable device and place the wearable around the subject's non-
282 dominant wrist. Fit the wearable tightly but comfortably around the wrist.
283

284 3.2. Connect the smartphone to a stable internet connection and verify the Bluetooth
285 connection is active.
286

287 3.3. In the smartphone, launch the PhysiologicalSignals app.
288

289 3.3.1. Wait for the app to display the word **Weared** in green.
290

291 3.3.2. Select in the configuration menu the **Change User** option, provide the ID of the subject
292 who will complete the tests and click **Save**.
293

294 3.4. In a laptop, access the dashboard and enter the test administrator's ID and password.
295

296 3.4.1. Select the subject ID and the subject's stress tab.
297

298 3.4.2. Check the evolution of physiological signals.
299

300 3.5. Take annotations about any relevant event occurring in the classroom in relation to the
301 student-teacher interaction.
302

303 Note: Relevant information and basic events will be used to label physiological samples
304 afterwards. Example events are a question from the teacher to the student, or a theoretical
305 explanation is initiated.
306

307 3.6. At the end of the lecture, ask the subject to complete the questionnaire about their
308 level of stress at specific times during the session, according to a 5-level scale.

309
310 **4. Data Analysis**

311
312 4.1. In a laptop, access the dashboard and enter the test administrator's ID and password.

313
314 4.1.1. Select the subject ID and the subject's stress tab.

315
316 4.1.2. Select the day of a classroom experiment.

317
318 4.2. Label the samples of the subject by identifying activities and perceived stress levels.

319
320 4.2.1. Identify lecture-room activities and their duration according to the starting and finishing
321 times and their types.

322
323 4.2.2. For each activity, select a perceived stress level.

324
325 4.3. For each subject and each session, download the file with the tagged samples.

326
327 Note: A comma-separated-values (CSV) file is created for each student, each row reflecting the
328 values of the physiological signals with their standard deviation, slope and diff, the activity type,
329 the activity-based stress (*i.e.*, the stress associated by default to the activity) and the subject
330 perceived stress.

331
332 4.4. Launch the data analytics package.

333
334 4.4.1. Choose a set of classifiers (*e.g.*, SVM, C4.5, k-NN, Random Forest, Naïve Bayes and Zero
335 R) and import the CSV file for all students for each session.

336
337 4.4.2. Train and evaluate classifiers using the 10-fold cross-validation technique.

338
339 Note: Depending on the analyses, activity type, activity-based stress or stress perceived, shall
340 be selected as dependent variable for the analysis.

341
342 4.4.3. Finally, check the results for accuracy and error rates.

343
344 **REPRESENTATIVE RESULTS:**

345 The protocol discussed was put into practice in a Computer Architectures course in the first
346 year of the Telecommunication Engineering degree at the University of Vigo. This course has
347 more than 200 students enrolled who are organized into 10 working groups. To carry out this
348 experiment, students from four of the groups were invited to enroll at the beginning of the
349 academic year. The project attracted considerable interest among the students, and around 30

350 students volunteered to participate in the study. From them, 12 students were randomly
351 selected for participation.

352
353 The COTS wrist wearable device selected for our experiments has HR, ST, GSR and
354 accelerometer sensors. The choice of this wearable was based on its variety of sensors and the
355 provision of real-time data feeding. Technical conditions in which sensor data is collected were
356 also taken into account. Data capture is performed at certain frequencies, generally imposed by
357 the operation of the sensors, but also due to the device's energy-saving characteristics. In the
358 case of the selected device, HR was sampled every second (1 Hz). The accelerometer offered 62
359 Hz, 31 Hz and 8 Hz as sampling frequencies, from which 8 Hz was selected because it offers
360 enough granularity for movement capture with reasonable energy requirements when
361 compared to the other frequencies. GSR may be sampled at 0.2 or 5 Hz. In this case, we opted
362 to gather GSR data once every 5 seconds. As for the accelerometer, this frequency provided
363 enough granularity while keeping energy requirements to a minimum. Finally, ST is sampled at
364 the same frequency as HR (*i.e.*, 1 Hz). Data collected by the device is transferred to the
365 PhysiologicalSignals app in the smartphone every second, including the HR and ST sample, the
366 maximum acceleration value, and the last value for GSR collected. To reduce HR noise, the
367 server applies to the received data a FIR filter commonly used in real-time applications²⁹ and in
368 the filtering of ECG signals³⁰, using a 15-sample window.

369
370 Information gathered during laboratory and classroom sessions is stored in the server's
371 database. This information should be downloaded to be processed using a data analytics
372 package. The set of generated data files contains raw signals' data and variables derived from
373 those signals. More specifically, for each raw physiological signal (HR, ST, GSR and
374 accelerometer), its standard deviation (st), slope (sl), and the difference between the present
375 value and the extreme value in the last 30 seconds are recorded.

376
377 The laboratory phase of the protocol was carried out in a comfortable room of the Telematics
378 Engineering department that has the appropriate conditions for the experiment. **Figure 2**
379 depicts the evolution of HR, GSR and ST values collected during one of these sessions for an
380 actual student. As can be seen in the figure, significant variations in the physiological signals
381 occur as the student performs each of the tasks (video, STC1, STC2, STC3, PASAT and
382 Hyperventilation) included in the experiment. A relatively high initial HR value can be observed,
383 most probably due to the stress induced when facing this task for the first time while being
384 monitored. The rapid growth of ST during the hyperventilation test is also noteworthy.

385
386 Also observed during the laboratory experiments were the remarkable variations in the
387 physiological signals at specific experimental moments, no matter that these periods were not
388 always perceived as stressful by the target student. This is due to the fact that perceived stress
389 is a subjective variable, and participating students do not fully agree in a common concept of
390 stress. During the laboratory phase, it was intended to generate brief periods of high stress.
391 These brief periods of stress were sometimes defined as frustration, but not as stress, which
392 leads participating students to respond differently to what their physiological signals expressed.
393 This effect can be visualized in the graphs in **Figure 3**. For example, in the interval between

394 12:15 and 12:20 (completion of the last test of the Stroop Color and Word Test) the strong GSR
395 variations are a clear symptom of potential stress. These strong variations are also present
396 between 12:25 and the end of the test (Hyperventilation test), but on both occasions, the user
397 claimed to feel a similarly low stress level.
398

399 The situation discussed above stresses the subjective character of stress evaluation in such a
400 short period of time. As a consequence, from the candidates for dependent variables in data
401 sets (*i.e.*, activity type, activity-based stress, or subject-perceived stress) we opted for activity-
402 based stress. This variable defines stress levels according to the level of difficulty of the task
403 addressed and not on the answers provided by the students about their perceived stress levels
404 at the end of each task. This way, video watching would be tagged as “relax” while SCWT3 and
405 PASAT would be labelled as “concentration” and the Hyperventilation test as “stress”. Note that
406 samples from SCWT1 and SCWT2 were discarded in our case because in a previous pilot
407 research was observed that, on average, SCWT1 and SCWT2 are activities that show a transition
408 between a relaxed feeling (reached during video visualization) and stressful one. For these
409 reason, we discarded from our analysis the signals from these 2 activities, and we included only
410 those from video visualization, SCWT3, PASAT and Hyperventilation activities. The HR, ST and
411 GSR variations among these states (relax, concentration, stress) are summarized in **Figure 4**.
412 This figure depicts the physiological signal quartiles for the three stress levels in the 12 students
413 involved in the experiment. In general, HR and GSR signals gradually increase as the student
414 faces tasks of increasing difficulty. Also, in all cases the temperature level is affected. However,
415 in some cases it increases for relaxed events and decreases in stressful situations, while in other
416 cases it occurs just the opposite depending of the person.
417

418 In order to analyze the correlation observed visually in the variation of the physiological signals,
419 machine learning techniques were applied over processed CSV files. To avoid initial transitory
420 variations for each task and level, only the last 3 minutes of each activity are considered in
421 order to avoid non-representative samples. In particular, several classification algorithms,
422 particularly SVM, C4.5, k-NN, Random Forest, NaiveBayes and ZeroR, were trained to detect
423 stress situations from the collected physiological signals. The trained classifiers became high
424 accuracy, low mean absolute error rates and high Cohen’s Kappa index level stress detectors, as
425 it is shown in **Table 1**. For all the 12 subjects and algorithms (except ZeroR), the accuracy of
426 stress detection in over 90%, mean absolute error value is near 0 and Cohen’s kappa index is
427 close to 1.
428

429 The classroom phase defined in the protocol took place during actual course sessions in the
430 lecture rooms of the School of Telecommunications Engineering. Several academic activities
431 were considered for this study: theoretical lectures; questions arbitrarily asked by the teacher
432 to the students about some aspect of the course; doubts or questions posed to the teacher by
433 students; short tests; regular exams/finals consisting of collection of problems to be solved by
434 the student in 50-70 minutes.
435

436 The visualization of the evolution of physiological signals in this case shows that variations are
437 subtler, that is, the differences in signal values for different activities are smaller than during

438 the laboratory phase. The most relevant variations were observed during classroom sessions in
439 which a regular lecture occurs after a pop quiz is completed. In this case, one or several of the
440 physiological signals suffer significant differences, as illustrated in **Figure 5**. This figure depicts
441 the signals captured for a student facing a short test (first part of the graphs). During the test,
442 the most relevant variable would be HR. It can be observed that the student has a higher heart
443 rate when compared to theoretical lecture time. In the same way, skin temperature is kept
444 relatively low when compared to theoretical lecture time, when it raises around 1 °C.

445
446 To analyze this in a numerical way, the correlation between the variations in the signals and the
447 activities addressed by the students, machine learning techniques were applied analogously to
448 the laboratory phase. The results for the combined pop quiz and lecture sessions show an
449 average classification accuracy of 97.62% (± 3.82) using C4.5. Note that for the analysis of these
450 sessions skin temperature was discarded due to possible biases in the final result. During the
451 transition period between the pop quiz and the following lecture students leave the classroom
452 for approximately 20 minutes, with dramatically affects temperature values.

453
454 A comprehensive formal analysis of the collected classroom sessions is still in progress. This is a
455 complex process where several challenging situations are addressed. First, abrupt short-time
456 variations in the physiological signals are frequently observed with no associated stress-
457 generating event. In most cases, these periods last for less than one minute without anything
458 significant being recorded by the researcher. Another incidence observed is the instability of
459 the GSR values when the wearable is not well adjusted or if sudden movements occur. Both
460 situations result in a very low GSR values, close to 0 μS . In a similar way, although much less
461 usual, there are incorrect ST values, close to the ambient temperature, when the wearable is
462 too big for the wrist of the user and therefore is loosely worn. To eliminate the analysis errors
463 derived from these situations, affected variables are discarded. Note that all the signals
464 monitored can be candidates to detect stress situations and different classifiers may be trained
465 using different combinations of signals, but anomalous values would compromise classification
466 no matter the classifier selected.

467
468 **FIGURE AND TABLE LEGENDS:**

469
470 **Figure 1. Tools used in the proposed protocol.** This figure represents all the elements involved
471 in the protocol and their interactions.

472
473 **Figure 2. Stress variation in a laboratory session.** This figure shows the different parts in which
474 the laboratory protocol is divided. Each part presents a clear variation in the physiological
475 signals.

476
477 **Figure 3. Stress variation perceived for a student in a laboratory session.** This figure shows the
478 discrepancies between the strong variations of the physiological signals of a student during a
479 laboratory session and their answer to the stress quiz.

480

481 **Figure 4. Physiological signal percentiles for 12 students participating in a laboratory session.**
482 This figure represents a percentile summary for each subject. The strong physiological signal
483 variations between each stress situation can be visualized.

484
485 **Figure 5. HR, ST and GSR variations during classroom activities.** Physiological signals variation
486 during a short test (Left). Physiological signals variation during a theoretical lecture (Right).

487
488 **Table 1. Accuracy, mean absolute error, and Cohen's Kappa index values obtained for SVM,**
489 **C4.5, k-NN, Random Forest, NaiveBayes and ZeroR machine learning classifiers using data**
490 **from the 12 students participating in the laboratory experiment.**

491
492 **DISCUSSION:**

493 COTS wearable devices are among the most popular consumer electronics products available
494 today. These devices are typically used to monitor physical activities, but their capabilities and
495 performance could be of great interest in other areas. In this paper, a protocol to evaluate the
496 use of COTS wearable devices for estimating stress in learning environments is discussed. The
497 definition of such a protocol is especially relevant in order to analyze different solutions
498 involving wearables and machine learning algorithms. The protocol is intended to be used in
499 educational settings, where the validation of stress detection procedures and their eventual
500 introduction may provide significant benefits. For example the use of wearable devices can
501 contribute to reduce the high levels of stress associated to the so-called burnout syndrome⁹⁻¹¹,
502 and as a consequence the dropout rate at universities^{12,13}, while improving academic
503 performance.

504
505 A critical aspect to consider is the Bluetooth link between the wearable and the smartphone.
506 This wireless connection between both devices may be broken during the test, so it is necessary
507 to pay special attention to it through the visualization of the data collected in the dashboard.
508 Although recovery is performed automatically after a short period of time (*i.e.*, an interval
509 ranging from 1 to 10 minutes), this interruption may cause the loss of the samples in that
510 interval. To reduce the amount of information lost, it may be convenient to manually reset the
511 smartphone device. Other aspect to be considered is the initial skin temperature sensor value,
512 as it may affect the achievement of skin stability, which may be delayed up to 10 minutes.

513
514 The main advantages of the protocol proposed in this research are its applicability to a large
515 group of students, its minimal need for support using automated mobile apps, its simplicity in
516 the preparation of the devices involved in the experiment and its low intrusiveness while
517 carrying out the classroom phase. This protocol provides a fast and simple method applicable in
518 controlled environments, such as classrooms or university laboratories. Besides, technological
519 abilities of participating students are not an issue, as the protocol is based in straightforward
520 technical concepts understandable by an average university student independently of their
521 academic field. As stated in the literature³¹, reproducibility in experimental sciences requires a
522 thorough and clear description of the protocols applied and the results thereof. The protocol
523 discussed in this paper has been designed in a modular way according to simple,
524 straightforward steps, which facilitates the reproduction of the experiments discussed and their

525 extension³². Among the most relevant design aspects facilitating reproducibility, we can name
526 the conciseness of the laboratory phase and its automated implementation by means of
527 standalone mobile apps. Additionally, the classroom phase does not require any interaction
528 with the students beyond academic activities. Most students pointed out the simplicity of the
529 process, and no complaints were reported in relation to their involvement in the experiments.
530 To sum up, collected evidence so far indicates that this protocol may be applied to subjects
531 with a broader profile and in fields different to education, such as health facilities or the
532 working place. Besides, this protocol offers the possibility to study several machine learning
533 solutions with which to test the best algorithms to implement depending on the requirements
534 of the experiments and on the wearable device selected. The use of applications to induce
535 stress and to provide a dashboard to display and tag samples facilitates the training of custom
536 stress models in a single laboratory session.

537
538 The main limitations of the proposed solution are related on the subjects' variability and the
539 reproducibility of academic activities. Recreating exactly the same conditions and situations
540 taking place in lecture sessions is practically impossible. On the other hand, the stress
541 experienced by each student is very personal, as in general there are different responses to the
542 same stimuli. In addition, there are hardware-related issues related to the wearable devices
543 themselves, such as different access methods, different sensors, access to physiological signals
544 in real time, or battery life. These technical requirements restrict eligible wearables to a limited
545 range of devices. In our case, eligible devices include those compatible with smart Bluetooth
546 capabilities and smart bands with a SDK compatible with major SO smartphone devices. The
547 number of compatible devices is expected to increase along the next years.

548
549 The proposed protocol is intended to serve as an instrument to eventually define richer student
550 models than those presently used in learning management systems or student information
551 systems. For example, the new information captured with the wearable device according to the
552 protocol discussed could be applied to the early detection of situations affecting performance
553 such as fatigue or stress, and to guide students to overcome these situations. An alternative to
554 this protocol may be based on wearable devices worn also outside the classroom in order to
555 detect variations in physiological signals over a longer period of time. This approach involves
556 several challenges, such as a constantly changing ambient temperature, or the subject under
557 study being forced to always be close to their smartphone to prevent data loss. Finally, this
558 protocol may be also applied to other courses and educational levels, which would facilitate the
559 capture of additional evidence on how stress influences academic performance for students
560 with different skills or fields of study.

561
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565
566 **DISCLOSURES:**

567 The authors have nothing to disclose.

568

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